

Kinetics of Thermal Behaviour of Halogenated Derivatives of Bisphenol-C and Bisphenol-S

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Bisphenols¹ containing cardo-groups (cardo meaning loop) are well-known for the preparation of epoxy resins. The physical and chemical properties are strongly dependent on the structure of bisphenols². Halogenated bisphenols³ are particularly useful in the preparation of flame retardant polycarbonates and epoxy resins. They are also useful as herbicides and fire-proofing agents for polymers.

Physical and chemical transformations⁴ can be studied by differential thermal analysis (DTA) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The shape of the TG thermogram is dependent on the kinetic parameters which are useful to elucidate degradation mechanism⁵ and to estimate thermal stability⁶.

Most kinetic treatments are based on relationships of the type

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = kf(C) \quad (1)$$

$$k = Ae^{-E/RT} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } f(C) = (1-C)^n \quad (3)$$

where symbols have their own significance.

$$1 \quad R_1 = R_2 = \text{Cl}$$

$$2 \quad R_1 = \text{CH}_3 \quad R_2 = \text{Cl}$$

$$3 \quad R_1 = R_2 = \text{Cl}$$

Results and Discussion

DTA thermograms were recorded at four different heating rates (β) (5, 10, 15 and 20°/min) in nitrogen atmosphere. The DTA thermograms of compounds 2 and 3 showed endotherms (first due to melting and second due to decomposition), and 1 showed three endotherms at 100–120° due to moisture and remaining two are due to melting and decomposition processes. The endotherms of 1-3 due to melting process (Table 1) and due to decomposition are observed in the range of 320–350, 340–370 and 345–380° respectively. It is evident that melting temperatures (T_m) shifted to higher temperature with increased rate of heating

since decomposition reactions are time- and temperature-dependent and usually increase in rate as exponential functions of temperature⁷. Such reactions tend to be shifted to higher temperatures with faster heating rates. They also tend to occur over a broader temperature range. Murray and White⁸ showed the quantitative relationship between heating rate and $T_{m\max}$. Kissinger⁹ and Ozawa¹⁰ utilised Murray and White's⁸ kinetic equation for evaluation of various kinetic parameters. Kinetic parameters for 1-3 were evaluated from peak temperature data according to Kissinger⁹ and Ozawa¹⁰ methods.

Kissinger method⁹ :

$$\frac{d \ln(\beta/T_m^2)}{d(1/T_m)} = \frac{-E}{R} \quad (4)$$

Ozawa method¹⁰ :

$$E = -2.19 R \frac{d \ln \beta}{d(1/T_m)} \quad (5)$$

where symbols have usual meaning. According to equations (4) and (5), the least-square linear plots of $\ln(\beta/T_m^2)$ and $\ln \beta$ against $1/T_m$ yielded the energy of activation (E) and is reported in Table 1. It is evident that the values of E by both the methods are almost the same for a given compound though Ozawa method is an approximate method. There is not much difference in the values of E for symmetric molecules (1 and 3) while it is about 1.4 times greater for asymmetric molecule (2).

The values of frequency factor A (min^{-1}) was evaluated by using peak temperature and activation energy (Kissinger method) data for 1-3, according to equation (6),

$$A = \frac{\beta E e^{E/RT_m}}{RT_m^2} \quad (6)$$

and are reported in Table 1. Other kinetic parameters for the melting process were evaluated (Table 2). It is evident that the specific rate constant (k) for the melting process increases with increase in heating rate β while half-life time ($t_{1/2}$) decreases with increase in β . However, there is no effect of heating rate on the change in entropy (ΔS) and the change in free energy (ΔG). The order in k is $2 > 1 > 3$, while that in $t_{1/2}$ is $3 > 1 > 2$. The values of k for 1 is almost doubled than 3 and it is reverse in case of $t_{1/2}$.

TG measurements : The shape of TG thermograms is dependent on the kinetic parameters which are important in

elucidating degradation mechanism⁵ and thermal stability⁶.

The decomposition temperatures at different degrees of fractional change (C) were recorded (Table 3) from TG thermograms of 1-3 at different heating rates in nitrogen atmosphere. The decomposition process is a single step decomposition and rapid weight-loss for 1-3 is observed over the temperature ranges 225-275, 250-300 and 300-350° respectively. From thermograms it is observed that 1-

3 are thermally stable upto 225, 250 and 300° respectively. It is evident (Table 3) that decomposition temperature for a given fractional change shifted to higher temperature^{11,12} with heating rate β since lower temperature decomposition occurs for shorter times. The rate of change of the measured parameter will also be greater for faster heating rate⁷.

Most kinetic treatments are based on equations (1-3).

TABLE 1—MELTING TEMPERATURE (T_m), ENERGY OF ACTIVATION (E) AND FREQUENCY FACTOR (A) FOR 1-3 DERIVED FROM DTA DATA

Compd. no.	$\beta \rightarrow 5^\circ$ °C/min	$T_m(K)$			$E (kJ mol^{-1})$		A min ⁻¹
		10°	15°	20°	Kissinger	Ozawa	
1	464.7	467.1	470.9	472.0	50.2	48.1	6.23×10^4
2	469.2	472.2	472.3	475.7	71.1	69.9	1.67×10^7
3	525.0	528.2	531.1	534.0	54.4	52.3	1.85×10^4

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS DERIVED FROM DTA DATA FOR 1-3

β °C/min	$10^{-1} k$			$t_{1/2}$			$10^{-5} \Delta G (kJ mol^{-1})$			$\Delta S JK^{-1} mol^{-1}$		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
5	1.39	2.00	0.70	4.99	3.47	9.90	1.23	1.25	1.42	-156.7	-110.3	-167.8
10	1.49	2.25	0.77	4.65	3.08	9.00	1.23	1.23	1.43	-156.7	-110.4	-167.8
15	1.64	2.26	0.82	4.23	3.07	8.45	1.24	1.23	1.43	-156.8	-110.4	-167.9
20	1.72	2.59	0.87	4.03	2.67	7.96	1.22	1.23	1.44	-156.8	-110.4	-168.0

TABLE 3—DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURES AT DIFFERENT DEGREE OF FRACTIONAL CHANGE FOR 1-3

Compd. no.	Heating rate °C/min	Decomp. temp. (K)						
		0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
1	5	468	478	510	518	526	531	533
	10	473	498	516	526	530	535	538
	20	486	518	531	543	548	556	561
2	5	468	488	498	506	511	518	521
	10	488	501	508	516	521	526	528
	20	508	531	541	548	556	558	566
3	5	568	581	593	598	603	605	611
	10	578	598	606	611	613	618	621
	20	591	611	623	623	626	631	633

TABLE 4—KINETIC PARAMETERS DERIVED FROM TGA DATA FOR 1-3

Degrees of conversion (C)	$E/kJ mol^{-1}$								
	1			2			3		
	Freeman-Carroll	Friedman	Ozawa	Freeman-Carroll	Friedman	Ozawa	Freeman-Carroll	Friedman	Ozawa
0.1	-	123.8	137.2	71.6	69.9	65.3	173.2	138.1	162.8
0.2	146.0	104.6	135.9	67.4	74.1	61.9	169.0	110.9	128.0
0.3	144.4	113.8	136.4	67.8	76.2	63.6	133.5	111.7	133.9
0.4	119.2	109.6	119.2	69.9	78.7	66.1	161.1	125.9	148.5
0.5	123.4	120.5	116.7	66.9	74.1	62.7	179.1	122.6	178.7
0.6	122.6	99.2	104.6	74.9	84.9	72.8	173.6	122.2	160.7
0.7	105.4	101.7	111.7	66.9	76.9	63.2	196.2	147.7	182.8
0.8	112.6	97.9	107.9	69.0	80.3	68.6	-	-	-
	$A = 3.09 \times 10^{12} min^{-1}$ $n = 0.16$			$A = 3.9 \times 10^{15} min^{-1}$ $n = 0.1$			$A = 6.9 \times 10^{14} min^{-1}$ $n = 0.46$		

In order to evaluate pyrolysis kinetic parameters methods of multiple heating rates were employed. The equations are as follows.

Ozawa method¹³ :

$$\log F(C) = \log \frac{AE}{R} - \log \beta - 2.315 - 0.4567 \frac{E}{RT} \quad (7)$$

Friedman method¹² :

$$\ln \left(-\frac{dW}{dt} \right)_c = \ln [Af(W)] - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (8)$$

Freeman-Carroll method^{14,15} :

$$\ln R_t = \ln A - \frac{E}{RT} + n \ln W \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where, } R_t = \beta \frac{dw}{dt} \text{ and } \frac{E}{RT_0} = \ln A + n \ln W \quad (10)$$

When $\ln R_t = 0$, $1/T = 1/T_0$.

Following equations (7–10), the least-square values of E , A and n were evaluated (Table 4). It is evident that the values of E is different for different degree of fractional change. The values of pyrolysis order (n) and frequency factor (A) for 1-3 are also presented in Table 4. The pyrolysis process is not a simple process but involves a variety of reactions such as cleavage, rearrangements, crosslinking, etc. Mass spectral data¹⁶ of 1 showed bisphenol-C, diphenylmethane, 4,4'-dihydroxydiphenylmethane, benzene; compound 2 showed 1,1'-bis(3-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane, 3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane, 3,3'-dimethyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenylmethane, toluene, benzene; and compound 3 showed bisphenol-S, 2,6-dichlorophenol, chlorobiphenyl, phenol, benzene fragments besides low molecular products.

Experimental

Benzene, methanol, chloroform, carbontetrachloride, phenol, *o*-cresol and cyclohexanone were of laboratory grade and were purified by usual methods. 4,4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl sulphone (bisphenol-S)¹⁷; 1,1'-bis(4-

hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane (bisphenol-C) and 1,1'-bis(3-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane^{16,18} (MeBC) and their dichloro derivatives¹⁹ were synthesised. DTA and TG measurements were made on a Perkin-Elmer DTA instrument in nitrogen atmosphere at different heating rates, viz. 5, 10, 15 and 20°/min; and 5, 10 and 20°/min respectively.

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References

1. V. V. KORSHAK, S. V. VINOGRADOVA and YA. VYGODSKII, *J. Macromol. Sci. Rev. Macromol. Chem.*, 1974, 11, 45.
2. R. N. JOHNSON, A. G. FARNHAM, R. A. GLENDINNING, W. E. HALE and C. N. MARRIAM, *J. Polym. Sci. (A1)*, 1967, 5, 2375.
3. H. E. HENNIS, US Pat. 3 234 289/1966 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, 64, 12603).
4. E. HEISENBERG, *Cellulose Chem.*, 1931, 12, 159 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1931, 25, 5982).
5. D. W. LEVI, L. REICH and H. T. LEE, *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, 1965, 5, 135.
6. L. REICH and D. W. LEVI, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1963, 66, 102.
7. I. M. KOLTHOFF, "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1976, Part-III, pp. 393-584.
8. P. MURRAY and J. WHITE, *Trans. Br. Ceram. Soc.*, 1955, 54, 204.
9. H. E. KISSINGER, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Standards*, 1956, 57, 217 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 3258).
10. T. OZAWA, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1970, 2, 301.
11. H. C. ANDERSON, *J. Polym. Sci. (C)*, 1964, 6, 175.
12. H. L. FRIEDMAN, *J. Polym. Sci. (C)*, 1964, 6, 183.
13. T. OZAWA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, 38, 1881.
14. E. S. FREFMAN and B. CARROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 394.
15. D. A. ANDERSON and E. S. FREEMAN, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1961, 54, 253.
16. H. H. GARCHAR, S. H. KALOLA and P. H. PARSANIA, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1993, 5, 340.
17. Jap. Pat. JP 8 235 559/1982 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, 97, 91937).
18. H. H. GARCHAR, H. N. SHUKLA and P. H. PARSANIA, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1991, 103, 149.
19. A. M. SEREBRYANYI, I. M. BILIK and N. M. MIRONOVA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 76, 85493.